

Condensation of Chloral with 2-Hydroxy-*p*-toluic Acid and its Methyl Ether.

BY A. N. MELDRUM AND B. M. KAPADIA.

A synthesis of phenylacetic acids has been effected by means of three successive reactions, *viz.*, (1) condensation of a benzoic acid with chloral (Fritch, *Annalen*, 1897, 296, 356; 1898, 301, 360), (2) the reduction of the $-\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{CCl}_3$ group to $-\text{CH}_2\text{CHCl}_2$ with zinc and acetic acid (Alimchandani and Meldrum, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 201), and (3) the hydrolysis and oxidation of $-\text{CH}_2\text{CHCl}_2$ to $-\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$ with concentrated sulphuric acid (Alimchandani and Meldrum, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 253).

The last mentioned reaction is not general. It is affected by the presence and position of other groups in the ring.

The present work was undertaken to study the condensation of 2-hydroxy-*p*-toluic acid with chloral and to extend the application of the method of obtaining phenylacetic acids.

2-Hydroxy-*p*-toluic acid when condensed with chloral in presence of sulphuric acid, yielded the 3-hydroxy-4-methyl- α -trichloromethyl phthalide (I). This was reduced with zinc and acetic acid when the phthalide ring opened and the 3-hydroxy-4-methyl-2 $\beta\beta$ -dichloroethylbenzoic acid (II) resulted. The compound (II) on hydrolysis and oxidation with concentrated sulphuric acid yielded the 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-6-carboxyphenyl-1-acetic acid (III).

The behaviour of the methyl ether of the acid was also examined.

On condensation with chloral and subsequent reduction with zinc and acetic acid it gave the 5-methoxy-4-methyl- α -trichloromethyl phthalide (VII) and 5-methoxy-4-methyl-2 $\beta\beta$ -dichloroethylbenzoic acid (VIII). The reduction product on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid yielded the 3-methyl-4-hydroxy-6-carboxyphenyl-1-acetic acid (IX). Here concentrated sulphuric acid hydrolyses not only the group $-\text{CH}_2\text{CHCl}_2$ but also the methoxy group to the hydroxyl group. To confirm this (IX) was benzoylated.

These reactions have also been applied to the production of phenylbisacetic acid by further condensation of the phenylacetic acid (III) to (IV), subsequent reduction of (IV) and treatment of (V) with sulphuric acid. The 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-6-carboxyphenylene-1:5-bisacetic acid (VI) was finally obtained. The attempted condensation of (IX) with chloral was not successful. The product of the reaction does not contain chlorine but it is the 3-hydroxy-4:6-dimethylbenzoic acid (X).

The action of sodium hydroxide on the condensation products (I, IV, VII) has also been studied. With the hydroxytrichloromethyl phthalide alkali opens the ring and hydrolyses $-CCl_3$ to COOH group. Thus compound (I) yielded 2-hydroxy-6-carboxy-3-methylmandelic acid (Ia) and (IV) yielded 2-carboxy-3-carboxymethyl-4-hydroxy-6-methylmandelic acid (IVa).

But with the methoxytrichloromethyl phthalide (VII) the $-CCl_3$ group only is hydrolysed, the phthalide ring remaining intact so that 5-methoxy-4-methyl- α -carboxyphthalide (VIIa) was obtained.

The reason for the orientation assumed for the compounds mentioned must now be given.

The *m*-linking of $-CHOH \cdot CCl_3$ group to the hydroxy or methoxy group has been ruled out of consideration for the following reasons. The compound (IX) was oxidised with potassium permanganate to 4-hydroxy-5-methylphthalic acid (IXa), m.p. 245°. This acid is not identical with known acid, 5-hydroxy-6-methylisophthalic acid (1:3), m.p. 270° (Jacobsen, *Ber.*, 1881, **14**, 2115) where COOH is in the *m*-position to hydroxyl group.

Hence the chloral molecule must have attached to the *o*- or *p*-position to the hydroxy or methoxy group.

The two phenylacetic acids (III and IX) are not identical. (III) melts at 213° whilst (IX) melts at 209°. The mixed m.p. is 200°. Hence again the chloral molecule attaches itself to different positions (*o* or *p*) depending whether the group present is hydroxyl or methoxyl. The substance (IX) was treated with chloral and sulphuric acid. With sulphuric acid (95 per cent.) the original product was recovered. But with the sulphuric acid (100 per cent.) the mixture after four days yielded two products, one with chlorine and the other without it. The first is a polymer of chloral, *i.e.*, $(CCl_3CHO)_n$ but the second is the 3-hydroxy-4:6-dimethylbenzoic acid (X) (Gunter, *Ber.*, 1884, **17**, 1608). This fixes the constitution of (IX).

The product (X) is formed by the elimination of carbon dioxide by the action of sulphuric acid (100 per cent.) in presence of chloral.

This elimination can be considered in the light of the "induced alternate polarity" principle of Vorländer. It has been found that the carbon dioxide is readily lost by a negative C-atom. Thus in (IX),

the methyl and carboxyl groups support one another in making the carbon atom which loses carbon dioxide negative.

Since the acids (III) and (IX) are different and since the chloral molecule $\text{CHOH}\cdot\text{CCl}_3$ in the methoxy compound is attached to the benzene ring in the *p*-position to the methoxy group, the linking in the hydroxy compound must be in the *o*-position.

EXPERIMENTAL.

3-Hydroxy-4-methyl- α -trichloromethyl phthalide, (I).—2-Hydroxy-*p*-toluic acid (10 g.), chloral hydrate (12 g.) and sulphuric acid (80 c.c., 95 p.c.) were shaken together to a clear solution. On the third day the mixture was poured over ice when a solid separated. It was crystallised from acetic acid and then from a mixture of acetone and petroleum ether in rectangular plates, m.p. 232°. (Found: Cl, 38.0. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_3$ requires Cl, 37.8 per cent.). It is soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, acetone, and insoluble in water, benzene, petroleum ether, toluene, chloroform.

Acetyl derivative crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 142°. (Found: Cl, 33.0. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_3$ requires Cl, 32.9 per cent.).

Benzoyl derivative crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 154°. (Found: Cl, 27.3. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_3$ requires Cl, 27.6 per cent.).

2-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-3-methylmandelic acid, (Ia).—The trichloromethyl phthalide (I) was heated on a water-bath with sodium hydroxide (200 c.c., 20 p.c.) for 3 hours. After cooling, it was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. A thick oil was obtained which solidified on keeping in an alkali-desiccator. The solid mass was purified through its barium salt and then crystallised from a mixture of acetone and toluene. The acid can also be purified by distilling the thick oil at reduced pressure when the vapours condense to a yellow mass. This on crystallisation gave the pure product as needles, m.p. 115°. (Found: Eq. wt., 223.4; C, 53.0; H, 4.3. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6$ requires Eq. wt., 226.0; C, 53.1; H, 4.4 per cent.).

The *barium salt* is soluble in water. (Found: Ba, 37·7. $C_{10}H_8O_6$ Ba requires Ba, 38·0 per cent.). The substance is soluble in alcohol, acetone, sparingly soluble in benzene, and toluene, insoluble in petroleum ether and chloroform.

3-Hydroxy-4-methyl-2-β-dichloroethylbenzoic acid, (II).—The trichloromethyl phthalide (I) (10 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid. Zinc dust (7·5 g.) was then added in small quantities while the mixture was automatically shaken. After 3 hours the mixture was filtered and the filtrate diluted with water. A white light substance separated. This was collected and crystallised from benzene in feathery concentric needles, m.p. 184°. (Found: Eq. wt., 247·0; Cl, 28·3. $C_{10}H_{10}O_3Cl_2$ requires Eq. wt., 249·0; Cl, 28·5 per cent.). The substance is soluble in acetic acid, acetone, alcohol, sparingly soluble in ether, toluene, benzene, and insoluble in petroleum ether.

Acetyl derivative crystallised from a mixture of petroleum ether and acetone, m.p. 185° (mixed with starting substance, m.p. 169°). (Found: Cl, 24·4. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4Cl_2$ requires Cl, 24·4 per cent.).

Benzoyl derivative crystallised from benzene, m.p. 140°. (Found: Cl, 20·3. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4Cl_2$ requires Cl, 20·1 per cent.).

Barium salt crystallised with 3 molecules of water of crystallisation. [Found: Ba, 19·7. $(C_{10}H_8O_3Cl_2)_2$ Ba, $3H_2O$ requires Ba, 20·0 per cent.].

2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-6-carboxyphenyl-1-acetic acid, (III).—The acid (II, m.p. 184°) (10 g.) was added to concentrated sulphuric acid (80 c.c., 95 p.c.) in very small quantities. The substance changed to yellow colour and hydrogen chloride gas was evolved. On heating on the water-bath, the whole turned to brown sticky mass, which was filtered through flannel and transferred to a porous plate. It was dried in an alkali-desiccator. The dry mass was crystallised from water three times in square plates, m.p. 213°.

The sulphuric acid mother liquor was diluted and extracted with ether yielding further quantity of the substance. (Found: Eq. wt., 209·8; C, 57·1; H, 4·7. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$ requires Eq. wt., 210·0; C, 57·1; H, 4·7 per cent.). The substance is very soluble in acetic acid, alcohol, acetone, ether, slightly soluble in benzene, toluene, petroleum ether, chloroform.

Barium salt crystallised with $1H_2O$. (Found: Ba, 37·6. $C_{10}H_8O_5$ Ba requires Ba, 37·8 per cent.).

Benzoyl derivative was prepared by the pyridine method. It was isolated by extraction with ether and repeatedly crystallised from

hot water in feathery needles, m.p. 126°. (Found: Eq. wt., 313.8. $C_{17}H_{14}O_6$ requires Eq. wt., 314).

The *methoxy* derivative was prepared by the methyl sulphate method, crystallised from dilute acetic acid and recrystallised from a mixture of chloroform and acetone in prismatic plates, m.p. 206°. (Found: Eq. wt., 225.6. $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$ requires Eq. wt., 224).

The *acetyl* derivative was prepared using acetic anhydride. The product was extracted with ether, and crystallised from water, m.p. 110°. (Found: Eq. wt., 251.8. $C_{12}H_{12}O_6$ requires Eq. wt., 252).

2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-6- α -trichloromethylphthalide-phenylacetic acid, (IV).—The phenylacetic acid (III, m.p. 213°) (6 g.) and freshly distilled chloral (9 g.) were mixed with sulphuric acid. After 4 days the mixture was poured over crushed ice. The slightly yellow powder was collected, crystallised from acetic acid and recrystallised from acetone and toluene in concentric needles, m.p. 249°. (The yields are improved by using 100 p. c. sulphuric acid from 21 p. c. to 47 p. c.).

The same substance can be obtained directly from (II). The sulphuric acid acts as the condensing agent as well as hydrolysing and oxidising agent. (But the yields are poor and the purification is tedious). (Found: Cl, 31.0. $C_{12}H_9O_5Cl_3$ requires Cl, 31.3 per cent.).

2-Carboxy-3-carboxymethyl-4-hydroxy-5-methylmandelic acid, (IVa).—It was prepared by the action of sodium hydroxide on (IV). The acid was isolated by extracting with ether and crystallised from ether in rectangular plates, m.p. 246°. (Found: Eq. wt., 281.5. $C_{12}H_{12}O_8$ requires Eq. wt., 284).

2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-5- $\beta\beta$ -dichloroethyl-6-carboxyphenyl-1-acetic acid, (V).—The trichloromethylphthalide-phenylacetic acid (IV, m.p. 249°) (10 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (300 c.c.) by heating. Zinc dust (35 g.) was added in small quantities at a time to the solution. After heating for 8 hours the mixture was filtered off from unchanged zinc and zinc acetate. The filtrate was then evaporated on the water-bath. The sticky yellowish syrup-like substance was kept in an alkali desiccator for 8 days. The mass was then treated with a small quantity of water and the white solid obtained was collected and dried. It was crystallised from water and recrystallised from a mixture of toluene and acetone in small white needles, m. p. 203.05°. (Found: Cl, 22.9. $C_{12}H_{12}O_5Cl_2$ requires Cl, 23.1 per cent.). The substance is soluble in acetic acid, alcohol, acetone, insoluble in ether, toluene, benzene, chloroform, petroleum ether.

2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-6-carboxyphenylene-1:5-bisacetic acid, (VI) was prepared by the action of sulphuric acid on the compound (V) (m.p. 208-205°) and crystallised from a mixture of toluene and acetone, m.p. 220°. (Found: Eq. wt., 265·2. $C_{12}H_{12}O_7$ requires Eq. wt., 268·0). The substance is soluble in acetone, alcohol, water (hot), insoluble in benzene, chloroform, sparingly soluble in petroleum ether.

5-Methoxy-4-methyl- α -trichloromethyl phthalide, (VII).—2-Methoxy-*p*-toluic acid (m.p. 164°) (10 g.) and chloral hydrate (10 g.) were mixed with sulphuric acid (50 c.c.). On shaking the substance went into solution. After 3 days a white mass separated. The whole mixture was then poured over crushed ice. The white pasty mass was allowed to remain in the mother liquor for 12 hours when it set to a hard mass. This was crystallised from acetic acid and recrystallised from dilute alcohol in rectangular plates, m.p. 132°. (Found: Cl, 35·8. $C_{11}H_9O_3Cl_3$ requires Cl, 36·0 per cent.). The substance is soluble in acetic acid, alcohol, sparingly soluble in ether, petroleum ether, chloroform, toluene, benzene.

5-Methoxy-4-methyl- α -carboxyphthalide, (VIIa).—5-Methoxy-4-methyl- α -trichloromethyl phthalide (VII, m.p. 132°) was heated with sodium hydroxide (100 c.c., 20 p.c.). The brown mass obtained by acidifying the solution mixture was crystallised from a mixture of acetone and toluene in rectangular plates, m.p. 222°. (Found: Eq. wt., 220; C, 59·3; H, 4·5. $C_{11}H_{10}O_5$ requires Eq. wt., 222·0; C, 59·4; H, 4·5 per cent.).

Barium salt crystallised with 2 molecules of water of crystallisation. [Found: Ba, 22·1. $(C_{11}H_9O_3)_2Ba, 2H_2O$ requires Ba, 22·3 per cent.].

5-Methoxy-4-methyl-2- $\beta\beta$ -dichloroethylbenzoic acid, (VIII).—5-Methoxy-4-methyl- α -trichloromethyl phthalide (VII) (m.p. 132°) was reduced with zinc and acetic acid. The white mass obtained by diluting the acetic acid filtrate was crystallised from dilute acetic acid and recrystallised from toluene in fine clusters of feathery needles, m.p. 195°. (Found: Eq. wt., 259·7; Cl, 26·8. $C_{11}H_{12}O_3Cl_2$ requires Eq. wt., 263·0; Cl, 27·0 per cent.). The substance is soluble in acetic acid, acetone, benzene (hot), toluene (hot), ether, insoluble in petroleum ether.

Barium salt is insoluble in water. [Found: Ba, 20·5. $(C_{11}H_{11}O_3 Cl_2)_2Ba$ requires Ba, 20·7 per cent.].

3-Methyl-4-hydroxy-6-carboxyphenyl-1-acetic acid, (IX).—The reduction product (VIII) was powdered and was added in small quantities to concentrated sulphuric acid. Hydrogen chloride was copiously evolved. The reaction mixture was properly shaken and heated and after 6 hours it was poured over ice-water when a yellow mass separated. Crystallised from acetic acid and recrystallised from methyl alcohol in prismatic plates, m.p. 209° (m.p. 200° in mixture with 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-6-carboxyphenyl-1-acetic acid, III). (Found: Eq. wt., 210·0; C, 56·9; H, 4·5. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$ requires Eq. wt., 210·0; C, 57·1; H, 4·7 per cent.).

Barium salt is insoluble in water. (Found: Ba, 39·7. $C_{10}H_8O_5Ba$ requires Ba, 39·8 per cent.).

Benzoyl derivative crystallised from methyl alcohol in needles, m.p. 170°. (Found: Eq. wt., 312·6. $C_{17}H_{14}O_6$ requires Eq. wt., 314·0).

4-Hydroxy-5-methylphthalic acid, (IXa).—The phenylacetic acid (IX, m.p. 209°) (4 g.) was dissolved in dilute potassium hydroxide solution (200 c.c., 5 p.c.) and the liquid heated on the water-bath. Potassium permanganate (300 c.c., 2 p.c.) was slowly added. After heating for 5 hours the mixture was filtered from manganese dioxide, concentrated to small volume and acidified with sulphuric acid. The white mass that precipitated was washed several times and crystallised five times from hot water, m.p. 244-45°. (Found: Eq. wt., 195·7; C, 54·8; H, 4·1. $C_9H_8O_5$ requires Eq. wt., 196·0; C, 55·0; H, 4·0 per cent.).

Barium salt is insoluble in water. (Found: Ba, 41·2. $C_9H_6O_5Ba$ requires Ba, 41·4 per cent.).

3-Hydroxy-4:6-dimethylbenzoic acid, (X).—The mixture of the phenylacetic acid (IX, m.p. 209°) (8 g.) and chloral (12 g.) with sulphuric acid (225 c.c., 100 p.c.) was kept for 8 days. During this time continual effervescence was observed. A reddish yellow substance separated on pouring over ice. This was collected and was found to be a mixture of two compounds A and B.

Separation of A.—The reddish yellow mass was dissolved in a small quantity of acetic acid (hot). On keeping a white mass settled down. This was collected, washed and dried, m.p. 130°. (The acetic acid mother liquor was kept for further treatment). The mass, (m.p. 130°) was dissolved in methyl alcohol which deposited a substance, m.p. 165°. This was crystallised from acetic acid and finally from toluene in concentric needles, m.p. 170-71°. (Found:

Eq. wt., 166.9 ; C, 64.9 ; H, 6.0. $C_9H_{10}O_3$ requires Eq. wt., 166.0 ; C, 65.0 ; H, 6.0 per cent.). The substance is soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, toluene (hot), benzene (hot), acetone, insoluble in petroleum ether, chloroform. *Barium salt* is insoluble in water. [Found : Ba, 29.2. $(C_9H_9O_3)_2Ba$ requires Ba, 29.4 per cent.]. *Acetyl derivative* crystallised from a mixture of acetone and petroleum ether in needles, m.p. 134°. (Found : Eq. wt., 206.5. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$ requires Eq. wt., 208).

Separation of B [polymer of chloral $(CCl_3CHO)_n$].—The acetic acid mother liquor from A was diluted with water. A pasty mass was obtained. The methyl alcohol and toluene mother liquors also yielded a yellow powder. All these substances were dissolved in acetic acid (hot) which deposited a mass, m.p. 115°. This was crystallised from methyl alcohol and finally from petroleum ether in rectangular plates, m.p. 120°. The results of six chlorine estimations were not in close agreement only two are given. [Found : Cl, 71.47, 72.56. $(CCl_3CHO)_n$ requires Cl, 72.2 per cent.]. The substance is very soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, acetone, benzene, toluene, sparingly soluble in petroleum ether.

The authors are grateful to Dr. T. S. Wheeler, Principal, Royal Institute of Science, Bombay and to Mr. R. C. Shah, M.Sc., A.I.I.Sc., for their interest in the work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
ROYAL INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BOMBAY.

Received May 12, 1932.

